

THE PROCESS OF IMPROVING THE LEGAL SYSTEM ON LABOR LAW IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: The legal reforms currently being carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan primarily affect the sphere of labor relations. The norms on labor protection established by the modern legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in our opinion, reflect the idea of contributing to the achievement of the main goal of all labor law as a protective branch - the coordination of economic tasks and the protection of the individual, his rights and freedoms in the field of labor, including the right to work in safe conditions.

Keywords: legal regulation, labor activity, investigation of accidents, working conditions

The concept of labor protection in labor law is considered as one of the principles of labor law; a legal institution; the subjective right of an employee to working conditions that meet the requirements of safety and hygiene in a particular labor relationship.

The set of norms regulating separate relations in the field of labor protection forms the most important independent institute of labor protection, which largely determines one of the main vectors of development of modern Uzbek labor legislation as a whole. Despite this, it should be noted that the works investigating at the dissertation level the problems related to the legal regulation of labor protection in the Republic of Uzbekistan have not been carried out modern period. These and other reasons determined the choice of the topic of the dissertation research.

The following theoretical provisions and practical proposals are submitted for defense:

1. The legal component should occupy a central place in the system of labor protection measures, since the rules of conduct created by the competent authorities are designed to preserve the life and health of employees in the course of their work. In this regard, the following version of the Law "On Labor Protection" of the Republic of Uzbekistan is proposed:

Labor protection is a system of legal, socio-economic, organizational, technical, sanitary-hygienic and therapeutic-preventive measures and means aimed at "ensuring safety, preserving human health and working capacity in the process of work."

2. It seems appropriate to include in the section "Labor protection" of the Labor Codes of the Republic of Uzbekistan definition of the following concepts: efficiency - the ability of a worker at a certain pace for a certain time and with a certain quality to perform a certain amount of labor functions necessary for him to work. ability to work - the ability of an employee to perform the functions necessary for him to work;

3. It is proposed to supplement the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan with a norm that discloses the concept of "healthy and safe working conditions", defining it as a set of factors of labor activity that exclude the possibility of harmful and dangerous factors affecting the worker's working capacity and ability to work or limiting such an impact;

During the classification of labor protection regulations, it is necessary to point out the important both theoretical and practical significance of dividing the legal institute of labor protection into sub institutions. In our opinion, it is necessary to distinguish the following categories by which labor protection standards can be classified: state regulatory requirements for labor protection, employer responsibilities in the field of labor protection, employee responsibilities in the

field of labor protection, state labor protection management, norms regulating the activities of labor protection services and committees (commissions) in the organization, norms, ensuring the rights of employees to labor protection, norms establishing rules for the investigation of accidents and occupational diseases, norms, regulating responsibility for violation of labor protection legislation, and the norms defining the bodies exercising supervision and control in the field of labor protection.

A separate issue in the framework of the study should be called the peculiarities of labor protection of certain categories of workers in both countries. In particular, describing the specifics of the women's labor protection regime, we note that since gaining State independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan has demonstrated commitment to the principles of tender equality. One of the legal outcomes of this policy was the adoption in 1996 of amendments to the Labor Code of Uzbekistan, which have a pronounced protective nature in relation to women and persons with family responsibilities. Note that these amendments have become a positive trend.

As a result of the analysis of the peculiarities of labor protection of underage workers, we concluded that the legislator, carrying out legal regulation of labor protection of this category of workers more often than in relation to adults, uses mandatory norms, less often grants the right to the parties to an employment contract to resolve these issues by agreement among themselves. This state of affairs is regarded by us as a positive aspect in the regulation of these legal relations due to several circumstances. Firstly, due to the peculiarities of their physical development, minors need milder working conditions than adults, and, secondly, due to the peculiarities of their intellectual and emotional development, minor workers cannot always actively resist the attempts of the employer to minimize their costs for creating special, appropriate conditions of complex protection, working conditions for such a special category of employees.

The variety of types and conditions of work constantly creates elements of

inequality, many of which it is not always possible to compensate through wages alone. In labor law, such elements are traditionally characterized as harmful and (or) dangerous working conditions. These features of a whole list of types of labor activity not only reduce the attractiveness of work, which may well be compensated by increased wages, but also lead to a deterioration in the health of the employee, an increased risk of injury, injury and even the possibility of death. The purpose of the dissertation is a comprehensive study of legal problems related to the regulation of labor of persons engaged in work with harmful and (or) dangerous working conditions.

The objectives of the dissertation research are as follows:

- to disclose the system of labor law guarantees, compensations and benefits;
- to analyze the legislative, collective-contractual, local and individual-contractual levels of legal establishment of guarantees, compensations for persons engaged in work with harmful and (or) dangerous working conditions in order to find an optimal and effective combination of them;
- to analyze the current state of Russian legislation and the practice of applying guarantees and compensations for persons engaged in work with harmful and (or) dangerous working conditions;
- to develop recommendations concerning promising areas for further development of labor legislation and the practice of its application.

The object of the study is social relations arising in the field of ensuring the implementation of guarantees and compensations for persons engaged in work with harmful and (or) dangerous working conditions.

The subject of the study is a set of theoretical and practical problems in the process of forming a system of guarantees and compensation for persons engaged in work with harmful and (or) dangerous working conditions.

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